

Institutionalizing Mentoring in South African Police Service in South Africa

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Abstract:- Mentoring is a mutually beneficial relationship in which a knowledgeable and skilled veteran officer (mentor) provides insight, guidance and developmental opportunities to a lesser skilled and experienced colleague (protégé). For this article mentoring is a unique interpersonal relationship between two individuals (Janasz et al. 2013: 1437). The article's main goal is to establish whether and how mentoring can be used to promote development.

The key purpose of mentoring relationships is to support and challenge both parties toward their learning and development (Parsloe and Wray, 2004; Garvey, 2014). Mentoring is to connect an individual who has a lot of knowledge and experience with someone who hasn't gained the same knowledge or experience yet. Parsloe and Wray suggest that when all the theory is taken away, mentoring is still a simple one-to-one meeting held regularly to support the mentee in their ambitions to make improvements either in their personal or working life. A mentor, therefore, is a leader and a counsellor, who relates on a one-on-one basis with an individual, usually a younger person called a mentee (Akinade, 2001). S/he focuses on giving direction and imparting knowledge. The relationship should be based on mutual understanding and respect. The mentee is aware of his/her need for guidance and deliberately adopts the counsel of the mentor after careful consideration (if it is about making a personal choice). Hence, the mentor is not imposing himself/herself on the mentee. The relationship is not designed to obliterate the personality of the mentee neither is it meant to focus on the superiority of the mentor.

Keywords:- Mentoring, Mentors, Peer mentoring, Professional development, Work integration, Police.

I. INTRODUCTION

In our personal lives, one seeks to develop our skills, continually learn new things, and challenge ourselves on a regular basis come with many rewards and benefits. This naturally takes a degree of devotion, with life often getting in the way of our self-improvement efforts. Having a mentor- that is, somebody who can help guide, advice and teach you through a problem or towards a goal- is one way to stay on track. Mentoring is a system of semi-structured guidance whereby the mentor shares his/her knowledge, skills and experience to assist novice police officers to progress in their own lives and careers. Mentoring is also viewed as a dynamic, developmental relationship between

two individuals based on trust and reciprocity, leading toward the enhancement of the junior member's psychological growth and career advancement and toward achieving mutual benefits for the mentor, mentee and organisation" (Pinho et al., 2005:20). Mentoring is the practice of assisting others in achieving their goals for personal, academic and professional growth and development by guiding, leading, supporting and challenging them via trust and respect for one another (Wright-Harp & Cole, 2008).

It is crucial to professional enhancement which supports novice police officers in the early days of their teaching career. The process of mentoring involves imparting knowledge, offering guidance, and emotional support, and cultivating and upholding a long-term connection (Mijares et al., 2013). In this process, a skilled mentor helps a less skilled police officer acquire the policing abilities necessary to fit in a policing environment and advance their career. Mentoring is considered to be a kind of professional support that is transmitted in different ways among professionals, colleagues and from an experienced person to a less experienced person. Mentoring is one of the best reforms in the education system and a very cost-effective programme that makes novice police officers capable in their workplace. Mentoring has a positive impact on increasing professional and vocational performance among police officers of all experience levels (Washburn, Washburn-Moses & Davis, 2012).

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework portrays the purpose of the study, to determine the influence self-development and mentorship have on police officials. The conceptual framework further illustrates the theoretical foundations in support of the study. Knowles' (1984) adult learning theory (andragogy) supports the perceived self-development independent variables. Similarly, Bandura's (1986) social learning theory supports the perceived mentorship independent variables.

Social learning theory is being highlighted more frequently as a crucial element of sustainable resource management and the encouragement of desired behavioral change (Muro & Jeffrey 2008). This theory is based on the idea that social contacts with other people help us learn new things. Separately, people pick up similar tendencies by copying the conduct of others. Especially if their observing experiences are enjoyable or involve rewards for the observed behavior, people adapt and imitate other people's

behavior after witnessing it. According to Bandura, imitation requires a true duplication of the observed motor behaviors (Bandura 1977).

SLT is arguably the most well-liked learning and development theory at the moment. Many of the essential concepts are shared with traditional learning theory. Given that it takes into account attention, memory, and motivation, this theory has frequently been referred to as a bridge between behaviorist learning theories and cognitive learning theories (Muro & Jeffrey 2008). According to Bandura, not all types of learning can be adequately explained by direct reinforcement. He included a social component as a result, arguing that people may learn new skills and behaviors by watching others. The elements of this theory suggest three broad principles for how individuals might learn from one another.

III. HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF MENTORING

One of the most well-known Greek tales, "Odyssey," is known for its advice and guidance. While he was absent, Mentor was trusted by Odysseus to train and instruct his young, inexperienced son, Telemachus (Hamilton, 1942). A new employee requires a trustworthy, non-threatening person they can observe and learn from, much like a small child. Archaeologists and anthropologists believe that shamans, cave artists, and medical men passed on their knowledge to younger people as early as the Stone Age (Shea, 1994). Blacksmiths would train a young apprentice to become a master craftsman throughout the Middle Ages (Murray, 2001). Before the first brick is set, a solid foundation must be established for masonry to succeed. A solid foundation is required for the wall to stand. The mentoring of new employees requires a solid basis for mentors, much like a freestanding wall does. In order for new hires to effectively acquire information and skills in learning the company and their new job, mentors need to have the organizational knowledge and time commitment (Mincemoyer & Thomson, 1998).

IV. MENTORING

Mentoring is a supportive, confidential relationship, enabling one to realize and achieve their potential. Mentors do not automatically have the requisite capacities to support and guide mentees in developing knowledge and skills (Barnett 1995). He contends that mentors must develop their capacity to develop others effectively. This view is supported by Cox & Ledgerwood (2003) who emphasizes that mentors must develop the skills they need to give mentees maximum support in attaining their learning and development goals. A less experienced person can benefit from mentoring because it is a process that includes coaching, counseling, and training and is intended to help that person grow both personally and professionally. Geber (2003) shows that mentors need to continue building capacities to deal with the complex issues they may encounter in mentoring relationships. Mentors who desire to promote the learning and development of others must focus on developing their capacities. The best way to measure the

impact of mentoring is thought to be how it affects mentee's growth and development.

Bozeman and Feeney (2007) note a collective sample of definitions that all identify various nuances that cloud conceptual clarity. For this research we have deployed the following definition:

Mentoring is a process for the informal transmission of knowledge, social capital, and psychosocial support perceived by the recipient as relevant to work, career, or professional development; mentoring entails informal communication, usually face-to-face and during a sustained period of time, between a person who is perceived to have greater relevant knowledge, wisdom, or experience (the mentor) and a person who is perceived to have less (the protégé) (Bozeman & Feeney, 2007: 731).

The context of mentoring is varied yet the doing of mentoring has similarities. Clutterbuck (2004:42) suggests that data collected from "practitioner accounts" illustrate mentors' competence in their role through their responses to protégés in terms of degrees of directiveness. He suggests that directiveness for mentors has two dimensions that lie on a continuum between stretching protégés and nurturing them. Mentoring is a mutually beneficial relationship in which a knowledgeable and skilled veteran officer (mentor) provides insight, guidance and developmental opportunities to a lesser skilled and experienced colleague (protégé):

- Mentoring relationship goals.
- To promote professional growth.
- Inspire personal motivation.
- Enhance the effectiveness of police service.

Mentoring practice by nature is a social and interpersonal process (Allen, Day and Lentz 2005; Kram 1988). This practice is a conduit through which learning can take place within the organisation. Through mentoring, educators can be encouraged to share their knowledge and skills with their colleagues. The deliberate utilisation of mentoring as a developmental intervention can encourage and enhance the sharing of knowledge and skills in the organisation and bring about change.

V. TYPES OF MENTORING

In order to lower staff turnover, police organizations have created new-hire mentoring programs. Other organizations, however, have opted for the more frequent approach of informal mentoring. There have been instances of informal mentoring throughout the history of law enforcement. An experienced officer typically encourages colleagues or acquaintances to submit applications for jobs in their department. As a result, during the hiring and training process, the veteran officer has a natural tendency to support, encourage, and inform his or her friend. By fostering a sense of belonging to the new department, this informal mentoring relationship benefits the new employee.

A. Formal and informal mentoring benefits

The emphasis in this article is on formal mentoring and so the focus here is on its importance in mentor development. Formal mentoring is designed to bring about change in an organisations and workplaces rather than at an individual level only. This type of mentoring nature of career and cannot be ignored in policing setting where changing policies and practices in the workplace are politically and socially important (Geber 2004). Formal mentoring involves the establishment of learning alliances for professional development and a commitment to social and organisational change (Geber 2003).

Mentoring with a transformation emphasis is particularly important in mentor development where mentors guide less experienced colleagues to help them achieve requirements for educational and organisational change:

- Ensures that all employees will receive the benefits of a mentoring relationship.
- Promotes agency loyalty and inclusiveness.
- Identifies program goals.
- Creates program structure and procedures.
- Defines mentor/protégé roles and responsibilities.

Mentoring Program	A d v a n t a g e s	Disadvantages
Formal	Progress can be tracked by the organization. Formal rules that have been set. All parties to sign agreement. Specified time frame that has been established.	Potential may be hindered. Less likely to be built on a foundation of trust – forces contact. Slows progress at a personal rate. Lack of a naturally occurring component.
Informal	Mutual understanding naturally developing. Mentor has a desire to instruct. Protégé has a desire to grow. The protégé's gifts have a mentor who is sincerely committed to them. Personal fulfillment from making a difference in the future. Helps the mentor prevent career stagnation.	Monitoring is improbable. Protégé may receive encouragement from mentor to pursue other goals. Mentor may instill in protégé unethical values. Due to the mentor's error of judgment, lost business resources were spent in the protégé..

Table 1: Formal and informal mentoring Advantages & Disadvantages

Adapted from Douglas (1997)

The biggest justification for establishing a formal process is that it gives every employee access to mentoring, encourages loyalty, and fosters inclusivity within the company. A structured mentoring process also clarifies the roles and duties of the mentor and protégé, establishes structure and procedures, and outlines goals. The program generally leads to increased employee self-esteem and a "wonderful place to work" environment, even if it takes time to create, launch, and oversee. Any leadership project can be improved and promoted through mentoring, whether a formal program is started or a mentoring atmosphere is established within an organization.

A partnership without official organizational engagement is known as an informal or self-selected mentoring relationship (Fagenson, 1989; Fagenson–Eland, 1992). Although it often requires some time to develop or occur, informal mentoring relationships frequently have a long lifespan. According to Ragins and Cotton (1999) and Rosser and Egan (2003), an informal mentor relationship is one that develops naturally or unprompted because of a shared interest rather than through the intervention of a third party. According to Kram (1983), mentors should identify with a new hire and wish to "shepherd" them to gain a deeper understanding of the company, just as they did. This seasoned worker serves as a role model for the new employee frequently. Informal ties frequently center on professional objectives and ways for a new hire to advance within a company. In an informal relationship, the mentor often prioritizes the new hire's interests to assist in defining

long-term objectives. New hires might be given opportunity to start working toward and achieving their goals thanks to mentors. In doing so, mentors provide new employees with the necessary developmental objectives and skills to be more satisfied in their jobs with vision toward their goals (Kram 1983; Kram & Isabella, 1985; Ragins, Cotton & Miller, 2000).

VI. THE POTENTIAL BENEFITS FOR MENTORS AND PROTÉGÉS

A. Mentoring Benefits for Mentors

It is known that mentoring creates benefits for the mentee and the organization with performance, motivation, knowledge, skills and change but less so for the mentor (Megginson et al. 2006) and that learning outcomes can be extrinsic and intrinsic (Jones, 2012; St-Jean and Audet, 2012). However, it is not sufficiently understood in the world of practice how both parties benefit. Studies tend to show the benefits to either mentees (Phinney et al., 2011) or mentors but rarely investigate the benefit for both parties together (Philip and Hendry, 2000; Laiho and Brandt, 2012; Snoeren et al., 2016). This study will investigate the learning for both parties. Thurston et al. (2012) suggest this is because mentoring is an opportunity for individuals to learn, realize their potential, make improvements, and to ultimately make changes for the better.

The benefits of mentoring go way beyond the mentee's personal development, positively affecting the mentors themselves, as well as the organisations they work for. The benefits are vast and as follows:

- Individual rewards are given to mentors for spotting and nurturing talent.
- The department's rules, practices, and cutting-edge policing methods must be understood by mentors.
- Mentors open doors for others, making their mark on the division.
- Mentors are viewed as valuable in the organization and are respected by colleagues.
- Mentors encourage innovation in their mentees by getting different viewpoints from them.
- Increase chances of promotion for both parties.
- Greater participation and visibility of senior leaders.
- A greater understanding of the problems that underrepresented groups face when it comes to policing
- Possibility to clearly engage with those on the front lines to comprehend current problems.
- Mentors “get by giving” (Sprafka and Kranda (nd)).

Another key benefit of mentoring for mentors is the effect on leadership mentoring has. Mentoring means practicing the core skills needed to be a successful manager, team leader and prepares for senior leadership. Frequently, people become mentors because they were previously protégés who experienced the rewards of a mentoring relationship. Others become mentors because they wish a mentor had been available to them during their careers. Whatever the reason, mentors derive great satisfaction from seeing a colleague succeed because of their efforts.

VII. MENTORING BENEFITS FOR PROTÉGÉS

A mentor is thought of as an experienced and knowledgeable individual with the capacity to instruct, mentor, and challenge a mentee by sharing knowledge, advice, experiences, and skills. A mentor views a mentee as someone who is motivated to learn and advance their personal and professional lives. The benefits of a protégés are the following:

- Increases likelihood for success.
- Mentors help protégés gain competency and avoid failure.
- Assists protégés in setting goals and charting career paths.
- Encourages and provides opportunities for new experiences and professional growth.
- Helps the protégé avoid pitfalls and learn through real-life examples.
- Enhances the protégés' feeling of worth to the mentor and the organization.
- Encourages self-confidence by cheering protégé achievements.
- Increase confidence and self-awareness.
- Enhance leadership skills and strong communication.
- Increase job satisfaction and support one another.
- Growing a new personal network and exposure to new and different perspectives.

The mentee will also find support outside of the line management. Widening their networks and exposing them to new ideas and perspectives. Through access to leadership, mentoring provides mentees with opportunities to develop that they might not have in their day to day roles.

VIII. MENTORING OF MENTORING FOR AN ORGANISATION

- Employee engagement.
- Employee satisfaction.
- Employee happiness.
- Retention rate.
- Promotion rate.
- Attracting talent.
- Representation of in leadership.
- Inclusive culture.
- Increase productivity.
- Breaking down silo (Cronin, 2019: 01).

IX. ROLE OF MENTERS AND PROTÉGÉS

Before defining the roles and responsibilities of the mentor, the goals of the mentoring process should be understood by the mentor and protégé. For example, consider a new hire mentoring process. Is the goal to, 1) provide a welcoming atmosphere that will anchor the new employee to the organization, 2) provide a career development mentoring process to help employees identify and map out career targets, 3) begin a mentoring program that ensures the continuity and quality of the next generation of police leaders, or all three. Once mentoring program goals are identified, the roles and responsibilities of the mentor and protégé must be established to avoid confusion and potential conflict and to maximize program success.

X. MENTOR RESPONSIBILITIES

Within the mentoring relationship, mentees must fulfill the roles and job-related responsibilities listed below (Meyer & Fourie, 2004):

- Encourage and model value-focused behavior.
- Implement what has been learned.
- Share critical knowledge and experience.
- Listen to personal and professional challenges.
- Set expectations for success.
- Help build self-confidence.
- Offer friendship and encouragement.
- Provide information and resources.
- Offer guidance, give feedback and cheer accomplishments.
- Discuss and facilitate opportunities for new experiences and skill-building.
- Assist in mapping career plan.
- Be willing to learn from the mentor and listen when advised.

The mentoring relationship requires commitment and shared responsibility for the protégé also. The partners should discuss mutual roles and responsibilities at the beginning of the relationship and review them periodically as necessary.

XI. PROTÉGÉ RESPONSIBILITIES

Within the mentoring relationship, the protégé must fulfill the roles and job-related responsibilities listed below:

- Clearly define personal employment goals.
- Take and follow through on directions given.
- Accept and appreciate mentoring assistance.
- Listen to what others have to say.
- Express appreciation.
- Be assertive- ask good questions.
- Ask for help when needed.
- Share credit for a job well done with other team members.
- Respect the mentor's time and agency responsibilities.

XII. ADVANTAGES OF MENTORING IN A BUSINESS

According to Meyer & Fourie (2004), context mentoring has the following advantages for an organization:

- It is a tool for creating leaders.
- Employees' career development may benefit from it.
- It encourages the sharing of skills.
- It encourages healthy working relationships and increases job satisfaction.
- When applied to a South African setting, it can be used to advance employment equity.
- It fosters a strong learning culture within an organization and helps employees become more competent and proficient.
- It can help the organization achieve its goals and can help employees realize their full potential.

XIII. CONDITIONS FOR EFFECTIVE MENTORING

If the mentoring relationship is to be successful, the following elements must be present:

- It is crucial that the required level of dedication to the mentoring process is present if it is to be successful. This implies commitment from top management, commitment from the mentors, and commitment from the mentees. If such commitment is absent, then the benefits of the mentoring process will not be actualised and it will not have served its purpose (Meyer & Fourie, 2004).
- Establish and clearly state the mentoring process's goals, objectives, and desired results (Blunt & Conolly, 2006).
- Carefully map out the scope, content, and workflow of the mentoring activities (Meyer & Fourie, 2004).
- Establish the criteria for selecting mentors and mentees, and ensuring that the correct mentor is paired with the appropriate mentee. There must be a high probability that the mentor and mentee will work well together and that their relationship will be effective and productive (Blunt & Conolly, 2006; Meyer & Fourie, 2004).
- Clearly define the roles and responsibilities of both the mentor and the mentee so that everyone knows what to

expect from the process (Blunt & Conolly, 2006; Meyer & Fourie, 2004).

- Training is required for both the mentor and mentee on the dynamics of the mentoring relationship and how to carry out their respective roles and responsibilities. The effectiveness of the mentoring process can be improved through training (Meyer & Fourie, 2004).
- It's crucial to continuously assess whether the mentoring process is accomplishing its goals. This holds true for both the mentor and mentee as well as the entire process. This entails determining whether each party is carrying out their assigned duties and achieving the predetermined results (Blunt & Conolly, 2006; Meyer & Fourie, 2004).

XIV. MENTORING AND RELATIONSHIP

Seek for similarities when selecting a mentor, look for characteristics you share that will facilitate a more intimate relationship. The reasons for this could be anything from being from the same city to having a love for swing dance in common.

- Be committed to the process both the mentor and the mentee must put in a lot of time, effort, and attention. Without commitment, the discipline required to carry out plans of action or agreements won't exist. This will cause the mentorship to fail.
- A mentoring should have definite objectives that direct its structure and subject matter and enable evaluation of the mentee's development.
- Before beginning a mentoring relationship, be sure that both of you are on the same page in terms of your values and principles. These will serve as the relationship's cornerstone. Establish regular in-person and virtual interactions to foster personal connections and trust.
- Create a communication strategy: Set regular check-ins for accountability and touch points. Make sure to recognize each success as a mentor, no matter how minor. Conversely, never pass up the chance to offer helpful criticism, regardless of how small it may seem.
- Are you prepared for a successful mentor-mentee relationship: The advantages of a mentor-mentee connection can change your career. Working with a mentor enables you to gain from their knowledge and expertise.

But in order to produce the intended effects, mentorship is a commitment that needs to be taken seriously by both sides. You'll be better prepared for a productive partnership with your mentor or mentee if you follow the above-mentioned stages. If you can't work with a mentor right now, think about working with a Better Up coach. They play many of the mentor's tasks, including setting goals, guiding, and holding you accountable, and they are wholly focused on your success.

XV. IMPORTANT CHARACTERISTICS OF A GOOD MENTOR

Gualardo, et al., (2013) describes the qualities that make a mentor effective and true. According to Gualardo, a mentor embodies the highest standards of instruction, accomplishment, and personal and professional growth.

Quality Challenger Mentor	Characteristic
Architect, strategist	Encourages the protégé to establish high standards. Teaches a protégé how to get ready for future trials. Possesses the capacity to impart strategic thinking to a protégé. Is focused on the details and recognizes the protégé's weak points. Position attained via knowledge, expertise, achievement, and errors. By being open and vulnerable, gains the trust of the protégé.

Table 2: Quality Challenger Mentor

Adapted from Gualardo (2000)

XVI. WORKPLACE COACHING

Workplace coaching is one-on-one learning and development intervention that is designed to support and enhance individual and organizational performance, and that uses a collaborative, reflective, and goal-focused relationship to achieve outcomes (Bozer & Jones, 2018; Passmore et al., 2019). Thus, it is an intervention with and for non-clinical adults (i.e., coachees) regarding work-related issues that is provided by a professional coach with no formal authority over the coachee (Grant, 2005; Grabmann et al., 2020). This definition thus includes coaching that is delivered to both executives and non-executive employees in workplace settings (Grant et al., 2010). Workplace mentoring refer to a mentoring hip program, implemented by an organization, where experience experienced employees help younger employees advance in their careers. They guide their mentees on their careers. They guide their mentees on their professional journey through their own knowledge, experience, and expertise.

XVII. RECOMMENDATIONS: IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF MENTORING

The following recommendations are made regarding improving mentoring:

- To make sure good mentoring are taking place choose good faculty advisors with good mentoring abilities.
- Faculty advisers, should be provided with briefings, workshops, periodic seminars to the mentors.
- Counselors can offer mentee's advice of up-to-date information on the full range of educational and career opportunities.
- Mentors should be Sponsor be involved in discussions of topics relevant to mentoring, such as professional standards, ethical values, balancing career and personal life.
- Mentors should provide guide to mentee's in advising their responsibilities.
- Mentor's should not abuse their power over mentee's including abuse of seniority.
- Mentors should be awarded for best performance in their work to motivate them.

XVIII. SUMMARY

There is no doubt that mentoring can improve an individual's job performance and satisfaction since the output is enhanced; nevertheless, a worker that is not self-motivated and has a disposition that undermines the learning process may not benefit much from the process. The mentor

at a place of work who wants to maximise effort for optimal. Outcomes may drive hard on the mentee. It is required therefore that there should be a significant intersection in the expectations of the mentor and mentee for mutual satisfaction. Mentors particularly should develop the character traits itmised above for personal fulfilment and for effective impartation of knowledge as more skills are passed down by example (social learning theorists). The mentee will eventually imitate the mentor.

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